

Complexes of some Bivalent Metals with Triazine Derivatives. Part-II. Complexes of Cobalt-, Nickel-, Copper-, Zinc-, Cadmium- and Mercury-(II) with 4-Amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine

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Complexes of 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (mtH) having the stoichiometry $M(mt)_n \cdot nH_2O$ (where $M = Co^{II}$, Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} or Hg^{II} ; $n = 0$ or 2), $Zn(mt)_2(NH_3)_2$, $M(mtH)_2X_2$ (where, $M = Cu^{II}$ or Cd^{II} , $X = Cl$ or Br ; $M = Co^{II}$, $X = 1/2 SO_4 \cdot H_2O$), and $M(mtH)_2X_n \cdot nH_2O$ (where, $M = Cu^{II}$, $X = NO_2$ or $1/2 SO_4$, $n = 2$; $M = Ni^{II}$; $X = Cl$ or NO_2 , $n = 2$; $M = Hg^{II}$, $X = Cl$, $n = 0$) have been prepared and characterised by magnetic, conductance, uv and ir spectral data.

In pursuance to our work on complexes of substituted-triazine¹, we report herein the complexes of 4-amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (mtH) with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} .

Experimental

The ligand was prepared by the reported method².

$M(mt)_2 \cdot nH_2O$: Hydrated metal acetate (~ 0.005 mol) was dissolved in aqueous methanol (90%; 40–60 ml) and treated with hot methanolic solution of the ligand in 1 : 2 molar ratio when bischelated neutral complex separated out immediately. The product was digested on a steam-bath for ~ 0.5 h, then filtered, washed with methanol and dried in an air-oven at 60–70°. The copper(II) complex was filtered without digestion, since Cu^{II} is slowly reduced to Cu^I . For the preparation of mercury(II) complex, an aqueous methanolic solution of $HgCl_2$ was taken and pH of the resulting solution was raised to pH 5–6 by adding methanolic solution of sodium acetate in excess.

$Ni(mt)_2$: Hydrated nickel(II) chloride (1.20 g) dissolved in hot methanol (50 ml) was refluxed on a steam-bath with the ligand (1.6 g) in about 1 : 2 molar ratio, dissolved in the same solvent, when cream coloured compound separated out slowly.

$Zn(mt)_2 \cdot NH_3$: Ammoniacal methanolic solutions of zinc acetate (0.005 mol in 50 ml) and the ligand (0.01 mol in 30 ml) were mixed while hot when fine crystalline product separated out gradually.

$M(mtH)_2X_2$ ($M = Cu^{II}$ or Cd^{II} , $X = Cl$ or Br) and $Hg(mtH)_2Cl_2$: The compounds were obtained on

mixing methanolic solutions of the hydrated metal(II) halide (0.005 mol in 25 ml) and the ligand in stoichiometric proportions.

$Co(mtH)SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$: Methanolic solution of hydrated cobalt(II) sulphate (0.01 mol in 50 ml) acidified with a few drops of concentrated H_2SO_4 (pH 3–4), was treated with stoichiometric proportion of the ligand dissolved in hot methanol (1.6 g in 40 ml), when reddish brown precipitate separated out immediately.

$M(mtH)_2X_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($M = Ni^{II}$, $X = Cl$ or NO_2 ; $M = Cu^{II}$, $X = NO_2$ or $1/2 SO_4$): The complexes were prepared as above but solid complexes separated on concentrating the mixed solutions to a small volume (20–25 ml) or by adding excess of ether to it. In case of sulphate, the metal salt was dissolved in aqueous 50% methanol. The complexes were filtered, washed and dried as given in the preparation of the first complex.

Uv and visible reflectance spectra and magnetic susceptibilities were determined as reported earlier¹. Mull spectra of a few compounds were measured on a Pye–Unicam SP-500 spectrophotometer. Ir spectra (KBr) of the ligand and its metal complexes were recorded in the range 4 000–250 cm^{-1} on a Perkin–Elmer 577 spectrophotometer at C.D.R.I., Lucknow, or on a Hilger-Watts H800 spectrophotometer at I.I.T., Delhi in the range 4 000–650 cm^{-1} .

Results and Discussion

4-Amino-5-oxo-3-thioxo-6-methyl-2,3,4,5-tetrahydro-1,2,4-triazine (mtH) may exist in thione and thiol forms (A and B) and can coordinate as ambidentate neutral or monoanionic ligand using either N–O or N–S atoms.

It has been found that in neutral or basic medium (pH ~ 8) the ligand is deprotonated and forms neutral inner complexes $M(mt)_2 \cdot nH_2O$ ($M = Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Cu^{II}, Zn^{II}, Cd^{II}$ or Hg^{II} ; $n=0$ or 2). The complexes with neutral ligand are formed in acidic medium (pH < 6). Nickel(II) yields two varieties of neutral complexes—one dull-red hydrated form $Ni(mt)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ and the other cream coloured anhydrous form $Ni(mt)_2$. The former is obtained in basic medium while the latter in neutral medium. The hydrated complexes do not lose water below 80–90° indicating that water molecules are either coordinated or closely associated in crystal lattices. The neutral inner complexes are insoluble in water

and common organic solvents like methanol, acetone and benzene, but sparingly soluble in DMF or pyridine. The electrical conductance values ($5-8 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$) of these neutral complexes at room temperature in DMF solutions indicate their non-ionic nature. The acido complexes containing one neutral ligand are slightly soluble in ethanol and methanol but dissolve fairly in DMF and pyridine. The negligible conductance values (Table I) of the complexes $Hg(mtH)_2Cl_2$, $Cd(mtH)Br_2$ and $Cu(mtH)X_2$ ($X=Cl$ or Br) also indicate their non-ionic nature. The complexes $Ni(mtH)_2X_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($X=Cl$ or NO_3) and $Cu(mtH)_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ are fairly soluble in DMF and methanol. In methanol they show electrical conductance value of $105-126 \Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$ indicating that acid group is ionic in solution in these complexes^a.

As expected, Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} complexes are diamagnetic while those of Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} are paramagnetic. The room temperature (300 K) magnetic moment value of $Co(mtH)SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$ lies in the range of pseudo-tetrahedral while that of $Co(mt)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$ ($\mu_{eff} = 2.28$ B.M.) occur in the range

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found(Calcd.)			Λ_M Molar conductance* $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$
		M	N	Anion	
$Co(mt)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Reddish brown	14.21 (14.39)	27.50 (27.37)	—	6 ^a
$Cu(mt)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Dark brown	15.53 (15.36)	26.82 (27.08)	—	5 ^a
$Ni(mt)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Dull-red	14.48 (14.34)	27.27 (27.39)	—	7 ^a
$Ni(mt)_2$	Cream	16.23 (15.75)	29.73 (30.05)	—	—
$Zn(mt)_2$	Cream	17.11 (17.21)	29.79 (29.51)	—	6 ^a
$Cd(mt)_2$	Cream	26.25 (26.34)	26.31 (26.25)	—	8 ^a
$Zn(mt)_2 \cdot NH_3$	White	16.35 (16.49)	32.04 (31.79)	—	—
$Hg(mt)_2$	Cream	39.51 (38.98)	21.41 (21.76)	—	—
$Cu(mtH)Cl_2$	Green	21.22 (21.72)	18.74 (19.14)	24.01 (24.26)	15 ^a
$Cu(mtH)Br_2$	Brown	16.40 (16.66)	14.35 (14.68)	41.52 (41.91)	20 ^a
$Cd(mtH)Cl_2$	Cream white	32.73 (32.91)	16.51 (16.47)	20.81 (20.76)	—
$Cd(mtH)Br_2$	Cream white	26.53 (26.12)	12.97 (13.01)	37.53 (37.14)	—
$Co(mtH)SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	Reddish brown	16.91 (16.87)	15.98 (16.04)	27.63 (27.50)	—
$Ni(mtH)_2Cl_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Bluish green	12.21 (12.17)	23.15 (23.24)	14.80 (14.71)	108 ^b
$Ni(mtH)_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Bluish green	10.89 (10.97)	26.23 (26.17)	—	105 ^b
$Cu(mtH)_2SO_4 \cdot 2H_2O$	Bluish green	12.68 (12.42)	21.26 (21.89)	18.82 (18.76)	115 ^b
$Cu(mtH)_2(NO_3)_2 \cdot 2H_2O$	Yellowish green	11.54 (11.77)	26.10 (25.94)	—	126 ^b
$Hg(mtH)_2Cl_2$	Cream	34.58 (34.13)	18.82 (19.05)	12.36 (12.08)	10 ^b

*In ^adimethylformamide, ^bmethanol.

of square-planar or low-spin octahedral cobalt(II) complexes⁴. Excepting neutral bischelate $\text{Cu}(\text{mt})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 1.53$ B.M.) other Cu^{II} complexes show normal magnetic moment values. The subnormal magnetic moment value of $\text{Cu}(\text{mt})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ may be attributed to super-exchange interaction^{5,6} or due to metal-metal bonding through the overlap of the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital of the Cu^{II} ions⁷. $\text{Ni}(\text{mtH})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows magnetic moment value ($\mu_{\text{eff}} = 3.13$ B.M.) similar to octahedral Ni^{II} complexes⁸. The magnetic moment value of dull-red compound $\text{Ni}(\text{mt})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is 0.32 B.M., while $\text{Ni}(\text{mt})_2$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{mtH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ show magnetic moment value of 2.38 and 2.56 B.M., respectively. The intermediate magnetic moment values of the complexes may be attributed to the existence of octahedral Ni^{II} species in square-planar Ni^{II} complexes as usually observed for nitrogen-sulphur donor Ni^{II} complexes^{8,9}. The proportion of octahedral species is high in $\text{Ni}(\text{mtH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Ni}(\text{mt})_2$.

The reflectance spectra of Cu^{II} complex $\text{Co}(\text{mt})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ displays two distinct bands at 23 360 and 21 830 cm^{-1} and a shoulder at 16 130 cm^{-1} . The former is assigned to charge transfer while the latter two bands to ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$ and ${}^2B_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively, in planar field. The complex $\text{Co}(\text{mtH})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows broad and strong bands at 17 860 and 9 090 cm^{-1} attributable to ${}^4A_g \rightarrow {}^4T_1(P)$ and ${}^4A_g \rightarrow {}^4T_1(F)$ transitions, respectively, in tetrahedral field⁴. The ligand field parameters were calculated from ν_3 and ν_2 transitions¹⁰ and were found to be $10Dq = 4 926 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B' = 964 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.99$. The value of $10Dq$ indicates that the ligand has fairly high ligand field strength.

The dull-red Ni^{II} complex $\text{Ni}(\text{mt})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ shows a medium band at 19 840 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1B_{1g}$ transition in planar field. The shoulder near 23 980 and 16 130 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{2g}$ transitions, respectively. The broad and medium bands observed for $\text{Ni}(\text{mtH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ at 10 590 and 16 130 cm^{-1} are assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^8T_{2g}$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^8T_{1g}(F)$ transitions, respectively, in octahedral field. A shoulder near 27 750 cm^{-1} is assigned to ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^8T_{1g}$ transition. The ligand field parameters were calculated and found to be $10Dq = 10 590 \text{ cm}^{-1}$, $B^1 = 636 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\beta = 0.60$. The reflectance bands of $\text{Ni}(\text{mt})_2$ located near 10 330, 16 950 and 27 780 cm^{-1} are assigned to ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 transitions in octahedral field¹¹. The reflectance spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{mtH})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ reveal a broad and medium band at 15 750 cm^{-1} assignable to ${}^2E_g \rightarrow {}^2A_{2g}$ transition in approximately octahedral field¹². The reflectance band observed at 24 390–25 320 cm^{-1} in Cu^{II} complexes $\text{Cu}(\text{mt})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{mtH})\text{X}_2$ ($\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or Br) and $\text{Cu}(\text{mtH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ is attributed to charge transfer band, while medium and broad bands at 15 870–16 950 and 12 450–13 890 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^3A_{1g}$ transitions, respectively in distorted octahedral field¹³.

From chemical composition it appears that Zn^{II} complex $\text{Zn}(\text{mt})_2(\text{NH}_3)_2$ has five-coordinated trigonal

bipyramidal structure while neutral bischelates $\text{M}(\text{mt})_2$ ($\text{M} = \text{Zn}^{\text{II}}$, Cd^{II} and Hg^{II}) are tetrahedral which is the most preferred geometry for the complexes of the metal ions with d^{10} electronic configuration.

The ir spectra of the ligand displays NH stretch at 3 296 cm^{-1} which disappears in neutral bischelates but remains unaffected in complexes $\text{M}(\text{mtH})\text{X}_2$, $\text{M}(\text{mtH})_2\text{X}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{mtH})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$. The medium and sharp bands at 3 010–2 908 cm^{-1} in the ligand and complexes are assigned to ν_{CH_2} . The strong band at 3 220 cm^{-1} and the medium one at 3 096 cm^{-1} observed in the free ligand are attributed to NH_2 stretches. These bands are shifted to lower frequencies by 20–30 cm^{-1} in the complexes indicating involvement of NH_2 nitrogen in coordination¹⁴. In case of hydrated complexes $\text{M}(\text{mtH})_2\text{X}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{Co}(\text{mtH})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, a broad band at 3 400–3 500 cm^{-1} and a medium at 1 615 $\pm$ 10 cm^{-1} are attributed to $\nu_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and $\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, respectively, of water molecule. The absence of $\nu_{\text{S-H}}$ in free ligand indicates that the ligand exists in thione form in solid state. The ν_{CO} of the ligand at 1 658 cm^{-1} is shifted to higher frequency or remains unaffected in almost all the complexes indicating that CO oxygen is not involved in bonding. The blue-shift of CO stretch indicates that CO oxygen of the free ligand is involved in hydrogen bonding. Medium bands at 1 547 (δ_{NH_2}) 1 395 cm^{-1} (β_{NH_2}) shift to higher wavenumbers suggesting coordination of NH_2 nitrogen to the metal atom¹⁴. The thioamide bands I (1 512), II (1 375) and III (1 242 cm^{-1}) of the free ligand are shifted to higher wavenumbers in the complexes indicating that thioamide group is involved in bonding. The thioamide band IV (891 cm^{-1}) is shifted to lower frequency by 5–35 cm^{-1} in the complexes containing neutral ligand indicating that thione sulphur is bonded to the metal atom¹⁵. In neutral bischelates $\text{M}(\text{mt})_2 \cdot n\text{H}_2\text{O}$, the thioamide band IV is located in the range 743–720 cm^{-1} indicating the coordination of thioamide sulphur by deprotonation in thiol form¹⁵.

The mull spectra of $\text{M}(\text{mtH})_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ ($\text{M} = \text{Cu}^{\text{II}}$ or Ni^{II}) display a strong and broad band at 1 380–1 383 cm^{-1} and a medium band at 821 $\pm$ 1 cm^{-1} attributable to the presence of ionic nitrate group¹⁶.

The ir spectra of $\text{Cu}(\text{mtH})_2\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ exhibit a strong SO_4 vibration at 1 113 cm^{-1} (ν_3) similar to ionic sulphate group¹⁷, and of $\text{Co}(\text{mtH})\text{SO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ display sulphate group vibrations at 1 235 and 1 088 cm^{-1} (ν_3 split) as broad and strong band and ν_1 (SO_4) at 975 cm^{-1} as a weak band. The ν_{SO_4} could not be located definitely due to ligand vibrations. However, from the range of ν_3 band (1 235 cm^{-1}), it is suggested that sulphate is coordinated to metal atom as bidentate chelating group¹⁷.

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